

Original Research Article

Sleep Disturbances and Self-Care Strategies among Women in Reproductive Age in Al Hasa

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Abstract

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Sleep is a biorhythm process that is vital for individual and good health. Sleep plays a significant role in brain function and systemic physiology. The quantity of sleep necessary for good health is vague. Poor sleep, either in number of hours or quality, may have health effects such as metabolic problems, hypertension, circulatory system disorders, diabetes, neurocognitive diseases and cardio metabolic outcomes increasing mortality rate. The aim of this study was to assess the prevalence of sleep disturbances and to explore the self-care strategies among women in reproductive age. A mixed methods design was utilized in conducting this study. A self-administered questionnaire was distributed to (500) mothers. The response rate was 62.4% which represented (312) mothers attending Health Awareness Exhibition in November 15-17, 2018. Face to face interviews were also conducted with 20 mothers to gain further understanding about the topic. In quantitative findings, the prevalence of sleep disturbances between the participants was 91%. (11.5%) reported that they had had trouble in falling asleep in most days and (7.1%) reported that they always had difficulty in falling asleep. (9.3%) reported that they had trouble in staying asleep in most days while, (1.3%) reported that they always had trouble in staying asleep. qualitative findings revealed that majority of the participants experience sleep problems. These sleeping problems are in some cases a result of childbearing and childrearing factors, and psychological factors. The strategies that participants used to solve the problem, such as ignoring the symptoms or trying to continue sleeping or resting in bed, watching TV or internet, eating food or drinking hot beverage, praying tasbeeh or reading Quran. A significant percentage of the women in reproductive age experience sleeping problems which are related to childbearing and childrearing and psychological disorders. Self-care strategies involved a variety of responses.

Keywords: Sleep disturbances, Self-care; Women in reproductive age.

INTRODUCTION

Sleep is a biorhythm process that is vital for life and best possible condition. Sleep performs a key role in the function of the brain and systemic bodily processes, including metabolism, hunger regulation, and the immune system endocrine system, and circulatory system functions. It is a physical and interactive manner,

essential for life condition and body management at any stage of life (Watson, 2015; Institute of Medicine, 2006).

However, the quantity of sleep necessary to be healthy is uncertain. Most sleep specialists, as well as the National Sleep Foundation, advise that adults obtain 8 sleep hours per night (National Sleep Foundation, 2002).

Healthy sleep needs sufficient period, good condition, proper timing and consistency, and lack of sleep disruptions or disorders. Sleep length is the most commonly examined sleep measure comparative to health. Additionally, the US Department of Health and Human Services created a Sleep Health Purposes to "increase the proportion of adults who get sufficient sleep" in Healthy People 2020, a federal plan to enhance the people's wellbeing (US Department of Health and Human Services,2015).

Unsatisfactory sleep, whichever in quantity or quality, can have a numeral of consequences for example, metabolic abnormalities, neurocognitive diseases and ever-increasing mortality (Kripke DF, 2002; Cappuccio, 2008; Cappuccio, 2010, Hoevenaar-Blom MP, 2011, Altman NG,2012).

Being a female is a predisposing factor for sleep disturbances. Female category has been steadily associated with sleep problems, involving too much day sleepiness, problem in initiating or keeping sleep, and night awakening (Klink, 1992; Soares, 2002). Also, studies had demonstrated that females report more sleep problems (Akerstedt, 2002, Lindberg, 1997). And have higher danger for a diagnosis of insomnia contrasted to men (Jaussent, 2011, Singareddy, 2012).

Different hormonal and physical changes at adolescence, gestation, and menopause, and all throughout a woman's life cycle can affect her sleep and lead to sex-specific medical conditions. Shortage of sufficient sleep or the occurrence of sleep disturbances can significantly influence a woman's daily life, including her social roles in the work and in the family(Lee KA,2008).

Self-care strategies involve a variety of responses. These strategies may be based on reducing or increasing activities or using herbal or medication or even over the counter drugs(Brown P, 2013).

With this circumstance, it is important to pay attention to the sleep disturbances of women and their strategies towards it.Quick care of the sleep disturbances may lessen the danger of expanding mental and behavioral complications (Blake MJ, 2017).

The aim of this study was to assess the prevalence of sleep disorders and to explore the self-care strategies among women in reproductive age in Al Hasa.

METHODS

A mixed method (cross-sectional study) design was utilized as it has been recommended that attitude surveys should preferably develop a range of tools to avoid promoting the status quo (Van Teijlingen E, 2003).It gives researchers the chance to give a broader overview and deeper understanding of the phenomenon(Johnson B,2007).

Phase I: For the Quantitative section of the study, the

researchers use a self-administered questionnaire which was distributed to (500) mothers. Purposive sampling was applied to collect the data. The response rate was 62.4% which represented (312) mothers attending Health Awareness Exhibition in November 15-17, 2018 in Al Hasa, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The questionnaire consisted of the following variables: -Socio-demographic characteristics: Age, educational level, occupation and number of children and items and statements reflecting knowledge and reasons for sleep disturbances.

Data were coded and checked for accuracy then entered into SPSS statistical software version 20. Analysis was performed by using the same statistical software package. Data were presented using descriptive statistics in the form of frequencies and percentages for quantitative variables and mean and standard deviation.

Phase II: For the qualitative section of study, the researchers used in-depth interviews with 20 women, aged 18 years and older, purposefully sampled from the participants for gaining further understanding of their self-care strategies. Questions for the qualitative section of the study were wide—permitting participant to answer freely regarding their self-care strategies. For the qualitative part, thematic analysis (TA) was done. TA is a method which uses themes to arrange the meanings of the responses of the participants.

The researcher interviewed the participants and explained the objectives of the study to them and clarified any possible ambiguity, to ensure completeness and adequate feedback of the questionnaires. A verbal consent of the participant was requested. Collected data was kept confidential and was not used except for the study purpose. Inclusion criteria include all women in the reproductive age 18-49 years old, pregnant women, nulliparous and multiparas, with and without previous CS.

For the use of the assessment tool, written permissions are taken via e-mail from Sherlock C who permitted to use the sleep questionnaire and sent us a Copyright License to Share or Remix copies of the tool. The assessment tool was translated according to standard guidelines. The pre-final version of the tool was obtained after a few minor changes done by the researchers and checking done by specialist. In summary, the original meaning of the questionnaire remained unaltered. Sleep disturbances are considered when the mean score is greater than 2.

RESULTS

Quantitative findings

Descriptive characteristics of participants

Table 1 presents demographic data for the 312 women. The table shows that more than half of the respondents (54.2%) were in age between eighteen and twenty-five

Table 1. Descriptive characteristics of participants

Demographic variables	No	%
Age		
18- 25	169	54.2
26-40	116	37.2
40≤	27	8.7
Marital status		
Married	159	51
Single	121	38.8
Divorced	24	7.7
widow	8	2.6
Number of pregnancies		
0	163	52.2
1	28	9
2-4	86	27.7
5≤	35	11.2
Number of children		
0	165	52.9
1	34	10.9
2-4	90	28.9
5≤	23	7.4
Are you pregnant?		
Yes	9	2.9
No	303	97.1
Do you have any mental/psychological problems?		
Yes	19	6.1
No	293	93.9

Table 2. Frequency and percent distribution for the sleep disturbances

		Grades	Insomnia
		N=312	N=312
Do you have trouble falling asleep?	Never	71(22.8%)	No (G1,2)
	Rarely	55(17.6%)	Yes (G3,4,5)
	Occasionally	128(41%)	
	Most nights	36(11.5%)	
	Always	22(7.1%)	
Do you have trouble staying asleep?	Never	143(45.8%)	No (G1,2)
	Rarely	68(21.8%)	Yes (G3,4,5)
	Occasionally	68(21.8%)	
	Most nights	29(9.3%)	
	Always	4(1.3%)	
Do you take anything to help you sleep?	Never	263(84.3%)	No (G1,2)
	Rarely	29(9.3%)	Yes (G3,4,5)
	Occasionally	14(4.5%)	
	Most nights	2(0.6%)	
	Always	4(1.3%)	
Do you have any medical conditions that disrupt your sleep?	Never	257(82.4%)	No (G1,2)
	Rarely	21(6.7%)	Yes (G3,4,5)
	Occasionally	19(6.1%)	
	Most nights	8(2.6%)	
	Always	7(2.2%)	
Have you lost interest in hobbies or activities?	Never	94(30.1%)	No (G1,2)
	Rarely	57(18.3%)	Yes (G3,4,5)
	Occasionally	102(32.7%)	
	Most nights	40(12.8%)	
	Always	19(6.1%)	

Table 2. Continue

Do you feel sad, irritable, or hopeless?	Never	88(28.2%)	No (G1,2)	151(48.4%)
	Rarely	63(20.2%)	Yes (G3,4,5)	161(51.6%)
	Occasionally	109(34.9%)		
	Most nights	26(8.3%)		
	Always	26(8.3%)		
Do you snore?	Never	182(58.3%)	No (G1,2)	249(79.8%)
	Rarely	67(21.5%)	Yes (G3,4,5)	63(20.2%)
	Occasionally	46(14.7%)		
	Most nights	12(3.8%)		
	Always	5(1.6%)		
Do you think something is wrong with your body?	Never	139(44.6%)	No (G1,2)	199(63.8%)
	Rarely	60(19.2%)	Yes (G3,4,5)	113(36.2%)
	Occasionally	73(23.4%)		
	Most nights	26(8.3%)		
	Always	14(4.5%)		
Are you a shift worker or is your sleep schedule irregular?	Never	117(37.5%)	No (G1,2)	168(53.8%)
	Rarely	51(16.3%)	Yes (G3,4,5)	144(46.2%)
	Occasionally	65(20.8%)		
	Most nights	41(13.1%)		
	Always	38(12.2%)		
Are your legs restless and/or uncomfortable before bed?	Never	126(40.4%)	No (G1,2)	173(55.4%)
	Rarely	47(15.1%)	Yes (G3,4,5)	139(44.6%)
	Occasionally	84(26.9%)		
	Most nights	35(11.2%)		
	Always	20(6.4%)		
Do you have any unusual behaviors or movements during sleep?	Never	209(67%)	No (G1,2)	252(80.8%)
	Rarely	43(13.8%)	Yes (G3,4,5)	60(19.2%)
	Occasionally	37(11.9%)		
	Most nights	16(5.1%)		
	Always	7(2.2%)		
Do you have difficulty staying awake during the day?	Never	161(51.6%)	No (G1,2)	221(70.8%)
	Rarely	60(19.2%)	Yes (G3,4,5)	91(29.2%)
	Occasionally	55(17.6%)		
	Most nights	19(6.1%)		
	Always	17(5.4%)		

Case considered with Sleep disturbances if had one question with grade 3, 4 or 5
Case considered without Sleep disturbances if had all question with grade 1 or 2

(The mean age of the respondents was 31.9). Out of the total respondents, (52.2%) were nulligravida and (47.9%) were multiparity. In relation to the number of children, (52.9%) had no children. Regarding the pregnancy, (97.1%) were not pregnant during the study time. As regards to mental/psychological problems of the respondents, (6.1%) had mental problems such as

Table 2 presents data for sleep disturbances. Of the 312 participants who completed the questionnaires. From the results (11.5%) reported that they had experienced difficulty in falling asleep in most days and (7.1%) reported that they always had difficulty in falling asleep. In relation to trouble in staying asleep, (9.3%) reported that they had trouble in staying asleep in most days while, (1.3%) reported that they always had trouble in staying asleep.

Regarding taking medication to help in sleep, (84.3%) never took medication while (0.6% and 1.3%) used some medications to get sleep in most days and always respectively. With reference to having a medical condition

that disrupt the sleep, only (2.6% and 2.2%) had medical condition.

In connection with lost interest in hobbies and activities, (30.1%) never had these feelings, while (6.1%) always had these feelings. Regarding feeling sad, irritable, or hopeless, (8.3%) feel it most of the days and the same percent feel it always. Referring to snoring in sleep, (3.8%) reported it most of the days while (1.6%) reported it always.

With regards to thinking something is wrong with their body, (8.3%) reported it happen most of days and (4.5%) reported it happen always.

Relating to question about shift workers or irregular sleep schedule, (13.1%) reported that it happens most of days and (12.2%) reported it happen always. Concerning legs restlessness and/or feeling uncomfortable before bed, (11.2%) reported it happen most of days and (6.4%) reported it happen always. In relation to any unusual behaviors or movements during sleep, 5.1% reported it happen most of days and (2.2%) reported it happen

Table 3. Prevalence of Sleep Disturbances

		N=312
Sleep disturbances	No	28(9%)
	Yes	284(91%)

Case considered with Sleep disturbances if had one question with grade 3,4 or 5

Case considered without Sleep disturbances if had all question with grade 1 or 2

*More than one answer

Figure 1: Self-care Strategies

always. Regarding difficulty staying awake during the day, (6.1%) reported it happen most of days and (5.4%) reported it happen always.

Table 3 illustrates that the prevalence of sleep disturbances between the participants was 91%.

Self-care Strategies

Participants who reported sleep disturbances used many strategies to help solve the problem. From these strategies, ignoring the symptoms or trying to continue sleeping or resting in bed is widely used (57%), watching TV or internet (50%) comes next, eating food or drinking hot beverage (30%), praying tasbih or reading Quran (18%), taking shower (16%), making exercise to be more tired (6%), using over the counter drugs (4%). Figure 1

Qualitative Findings

Participants described trying a variety of techniques to help enhance their sleep. These practices include the use

of selected substances, over-the-counter medications, and non-pharmacologic approaches such as meditation, reading, watching television, exercising, and reading Quran and Prying.

We discussed the most important themes that emerged through our data analysis. While acknowledging considerable overlap and interplay among them, we grouped these themes into the following categories: 1: Describing the cause of the problem with two subthemes (childbearing and childrearing factors, psychological factors). 2: Self-Care Strategies.

Theme one: Describing the cause of the problem

Subtheme one: Childbearing and childrearing factors

A full night's sleep was seen as 'something to look forward to', despite being a rare experience. One of the participants said "Poor sleep is one of my problems, I can't be fair between my responsibilities as a mother and my rights. So, I feel uncomfortable to go to bed. I always think something is missing; I can't stop thinking about it."

Another participant had a lot of tasks at home, work

and feels bad for this. The participant described, "I have a lot of tasks for my children, husband, work, home, and I can't finish all of my duties. When can I sleep?"

Subtheme two: Psychological factors

The experience of a delayed sleep, characteristic of the changes in sleep, was clearly described by participants. For example, one of them described, "I feel bad and can't sleep alone. I need to feel secure."

One participant summarized her problem with sleep as, "I have nothing to do all day. No need to sleep". Another one said, "It's my nature, I can't sleep more than 4 hours per day and in some days do not continue sleep". One of them also said, "I have a lot of problems. I can't give up thinking about it. Thinking about my problems is my problem". Another participant who is having bad dreams said, "I suffer from bad dreams. I hate to fall asleep". Another one suffering from loneliness said, "Feeling the loneliness is my problem".

Theme Two: Self-Care Strategies

Participants described sleep disturbances as extending beyond nighttime difficulties and having substantial effects on their social and family role which they need to cope with. The styles of current self-care strategies mentioned by the respondents ranged from altering diet or exercise patterns, watching television, lying in bed, getting up to engage in some activity, listening to Holy Quran or drinking herbal drinks or warm milk, changing the sleep location, meditating, taking hot baths and taking OTC medication.

For one participant, she said, "I take warm shower immediately before sleeping, or try to do some physical exercise before sleeping time to help my body and brain to relax".

Another one mentioned, "I drink warm milk or warm chamomile. It helps me to sleep. Also, I prefer to close all lights and be away from any noise".

For one participant who has insomnia, she developed distinct sleeping habits such as sleeping in her children's room. She said, "When I want to sleep deeply, I go to my children's room, to sleep between them". One of the participants feel loneliness and said, "The best thing I do is to stop thinking, but it's difficult to stop thinking when I am alone."

There are also some creative methods used to solve sleep disturbance problem by the participants. One of them described, "Before sleeping, I try to empty my mind, so I watch an internet program in my mobile while I am laying on bed." Another one said, "I eat a lot of food to fill my stomach to waste my time until sleep comes". In the same idea, another participant said, "the best practice to fall asleep is reading a board book".

Another participant said, "I took a medication prescribed by my physician and medication not prescribed in some days to help me to fall asleep".

One of the participants believes that help from god will solve her problem and described this as "I believe that prayer and Tasbih is my solution to fall asleep". Same thing is verbalized by another participant saying, "Reading Quran and praying give me relaxation until I sleep."

DISCUSSION

For quantitative findings

This study sought to capture in-depth descriptions of the self-care strategies among women in Al Hasa and the prevalence of sleep disturbances between them. The participants in this study reported that they had experienced difficulty in falling asleep in most days. These findings are similar to Pearson NJ (2006) study who found that the majority of participants reported that they had experienced difficulty sleeping during the previous 24 hours on one or more days.

In the present study the primary response to the sleep disturbances was not to seek help or medical advice or ignore the symptoms. They took it as a personal problem, and they try to do some strategies to solve the problem. This finding is different from Stinson et al., (2006) who found that the participants considered the sleeping disorders common in their families and reasoning it that it is not uncommon among them.

Regarding taking medication or asking help to sleep, in this study the majority never took medication. These results are same with Goodwin JS (1999) study who found that the most commonly reported self-care strategies used by older adults were to ignore their sleep difficulty or see how it progressed, stay in bed or rest, and pray. However, this contrasted with Henry D. who found that when help was sought from a medical practitioner, one-third of the sample sought help directly from a sleep specialist, and two-thirds first went to a practitioner with whom they already had a relationship.

There is a huge number of researches examining the link between sleep and health-related outcomes. For example, insufficient sleep has been linked to increased psychological stress (Cruess et al., 2003) and lower self-rated health (Steptoe et al., 2006). Obtaining optimal levels of sleep is also associated with better health-related quality of life (Loprinzi P. D, Joyner C., 2018).

For qualitative findings

Almost of the study participant had cause or more for sleep disturbances. Some of these causes related to

childbearing and rearing but others related to psychological factors.

In this study, the self-care strategies for sleep disturbances that the participants reported are of a variety of methods, including non-pharmacologic methods such as, meditation, reading, watching television, exercising and hard work, and reading Quran and praying and over-the-counter medications.

These results were in association with Henry D (2013) research that has reported that styles of self-treatment of symptoms ranged from taking OTC medication or dietary supplements, altering diet or exercise patterns, watching television, doing yoga, lying in bed, getting up to engage in some activity, listening to subliminal tapes or engaging in self-hypnosis, trying acupuncture, drinking alcohol, drinking herbal tea or warm milk, purchasing a better mattress, trying massages, changing the sleep location, meditating, taking hot baths, and napping.

These results contrast with another study who found that the participants reported they had not used herbal remedies or supplements, (Morin CM, 2006).

CONCLUSION

Sleep problems are more common in women throughout the life cycle and, in some cases, are associated with or exacerbated by reproductive-related events. Quite often, concurrent treatment strategies are done to remedy the problem. Self-care strategies involve a variety of responses. These strategies may be based on reducing or increasing activities or using herbal or medication or even over the counter drugs

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